

Sound Symbolism and Dimensionality

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Abstract: The bouba/kiki paradigm is a product of sound symbolism, the linguistic phenomenon of meaning/sound associations. First documented in 1929, the paradigm has become the focus of numerous studies. However, despite being so well-attested, there is no single, accepted explanation for its existence. In the present study, I take D’Onofrio’s (2014) position, which suggests the influence of vowel frontness and backness on the paradigm. D’Onofrio (2014) is novel in that it departs from the abstract, two-dimensional stimuli characteristic of previous studies instead uses familiar, three-dimensional objects as stimuli. After providing a brief overview of D’Onofrio (2014) and other literature, I introduce an online experiment designed to take our knowledge of this paradigm further. As in D’Onofrio (2014), I use three-dimensional stimuli, but introduce another element: physical movement via GIFs. This places the paradigm further into the real world by simulating physical interaction. My hypotheses are twofold: first, that form-meaning association is significantly influenced by three-dimensionality; and second, that the perceived ‘sharpness’ or ‘roundness’ of the stimuli is boosted by the three-dimensionality of these properties. It is important to note, however, that no data has been collected regarding this experiment. This writeup only summarises the aims of the experiment created and introduces a proposal for its use, and does not make any data-driven claims about these hypotheses. This proposal and the experiment serve only as a suggestion for the direction of future work.

Keywords: sound symbolism; dimensionality; vowel quality; phonetics; phonology; cognition

1 Background

Sound symbolism is the linguistic phenomenon of meaning/sound association. The bouba/kiki effect is one of its most well-known paradigms, first documented by Wolfgang Köhler (1929) and replicated ad infinitum, notably by Ramachandran and Hubbard (2001) who coined the labels ‘bouba’ and ‘kiki’. In this paradigm, rounded objects are consistently paired with words also perceived to be round (like ‘bouba’) and spiked objects are paired with those perceived to be sharper (like ‘kiki’). There have been various explanations for this; Ramachandran and Hubbard (2001) suggested influence of the mouth’s roundness when producing the word ‘bouba’ and tautness when producing ‘kiki.’ Other studies have considered the role of different consonants, vowel quality, and even vowel quantity (Bross 2018).

In a novel approach, D’Onofrio (2014) considers vowel frontness and backness. Additionally, she departs from previous studies (Ramachandran and Hubbard (2001); Maurer (2006)) which have only used abstract, two-dimensional shapes as stimuli, and instead uses familiar, three-dimensional objects. D’Onofrio (2014) finds that vowel frontness and backness are significantly influenced by the dimensionality of an object; perceived roundness was associated with back vowels and perceived spikiness with front vowels. This expands the paradigm’s reach, situating it in the real world.

In this writeup, I continue D’Onofrio’s exploration and investigate the extent of the paradigm’s real-world applications by proposing an experiment which introduces three-dimensional GIFs as stimuli, simulating tactile interaction. I maintain that investigating language users’ conceptions of dimensionality, especially three dimensionality, is the next step in understanding the cognitive processes behind sound symbolic associations.

2 Motivation

Like D’Onofrio (2014), gaps in the literature motivated my decision to use three dimensional objects. Many studies have only tested dimensionality relative to two dimensions. For example, Bankieris et al. (2015) and Cuskley et al. (2019) found sound-symbolic associations with vowel category were weakest when the domain of meaning was directional (up/down) or spatial. However, both these domains are situated on the X/Y axis; exploring the introduction of a Z-axis – three dimensionality – may elicit different results.

Indeed, D’Onofrio’s (2014) findings suggest that the Z-axis plays an untapped role in sound-symbolic associations. Notably, D’Onofrio (2014) found that stimuli with three-dimensional conceptions of ‘roundness’ were even *more* significant predictors of vowel backness than stimuli with two-dimensional ‘roundness.’ The newfound significance of three-dimensionality has implications for the presence of the bouba/kiki paradigm and sound symbolism in the real world. It suggests that these phenomena may be more common cognitive processes than previously thought, perhaps often activated in our daily lives where we constantly interact with three-dimensional objects.

This finding abstractly contradicts Bankieris et al. (2015) and Cuskley et al.’s (2019) findings that X/Y axis dimensionality did not correspond positively to sound symbolic associations. However, it may be that dimensionality must be form-related, not meaning-related, to be significant, or that X/Y axis dimensionality is not as salient a predictor as Z-axis.

2.1 Departing from D’Onofrio (2014)

The present experiment puts D’Onofrio’s (2014) preliminary findings on three dimensionality at the forefront, expanding the number of stimuli used and focusing directly on dimensionality’s role, rather than observing it as a secondary finding. Further, though D’Onofrio (2014) found three-dimensionality a significant predictor, this result only applied to three-dimensional *roundness*. Therefore, in this experiment, I have used the same procedure for spikiness to determine if either more data or learning bring out the same effect.

3 Research questions

Primarily, my experiment investigates whether using interactive 3D rendered stimuli influences the vowel quality of participants’ object descriptions.

The combination of sound symbolism and iterated learning also allows for an examination of their interaction, that is, whether one takes precedence over another; will the bouba/kiki paradigm (or broader facets of sound symbolism) override learning?

My predictions are as follows:

1. form-meaning association is significantly influenced by three-dimensionality
 - a. and if it is, this will be shown by convergence to the predicted vowel quality (either backness or frontness) when paired with the opposite one
2. the perceived ‘sharpness’ or ‘roundness’ of the stimuli is boosted by the three-dimensionality of these properties
 - a. and if it is, the vowel association effects will be boosted

4 Experimental design and set-up

4.1 Experiment technicality and functionality

The present experiment was coded using JavaScript and the JsPsych behavioural experiment framework and runs on any desktop browser. The code is not yet open source accessible as this work is ongoing.

The experiment tests a corpus of 18 form-meaning pairs of real-world objects and ‘alien’ labels. The experiment begins with several instruction and consent screens, telling participants they will be learning a created ‘alien’ language. The instructions ensure the participant has configured their audio correctly, so as not to lose any data unnecessarily.

Participants then enter the learning phase and are exposed to a randomised subset of ten object-label pairs. They then move on to the production phase, where they must record their own audio labels for the entire corpus of 18 pairs. The subset in the learning phase simulates a bottleneck on transmission in order to observe convergence to a certain form.

4.2 Visual and audio stimuli

The visual stimuli are divided evenly between three spiky and three round forms with three variations on dimensionality each: a 2D image, a 3D static image, and a 3D GIF. Within the round or spiky groupings, two are classically round or spiky, and one is in the middle, termed the ‘blend.’ The blend has been added to investigate which of the two form qualities, round or spiky, is more salient by observing which prevails during the labelling process. Since D’Onofrio did not find three-dimensionality significant for spikiness, my introduction of the blend secondarily investigates the strength of (or discrepancy between) the form qualities themselves.

All visual stimuli are familiar objects in order to simulate as close as possible a real-world experience. See Appendix A for all visual stimuli. The auditory stimuli are the same as in D’Onofrio (2014), given below in Figure 1. The original audio files were not made available for reuse, and were re-recorded for the purposes of this experiment.

Table 3. Pool of martian words for the real-world object task.

Condition	Front vowels		Back vowels	
	/i/	/e/	/u/	/a/
1	/pimə/	/pemə/	/pumə/	/pamə/
2	/bimə/	/bemə/	/bumə/	/bamə/
3	/timə/	/temə/	/tumə/	/tamə/
4	/dimə/	/demə/	/dumə/	/damə/
5	/kimə/	/kemə/	/kumə/	/kamə/
6	/gimə/	/gemə/	/gumə/	/gamə/

Figure 1: Original audio stimuli for generation 0.

4.3 Reasoning for dimensionality variations

Splitting dimensionality into three variations, each more physically dimensional than the previous, will allow me to total the proportion of vowel backness for each and thus more accurately measure how dimensionality influences results.

This approach takes from D’Onofrio (2014), where she refines the original bouba/kiki experiment by individually testing possible influencing features (such as vowel height or mouth shape)

to see what each brings to sound symbolic associations. D’Onofrio essentially reverse engineers the paradigm, working backwards to determine which features are responsible for which associations. This helps to more fully understand the cognitive process; I believe this is an equally relevant tactic for the present experiment.

For each object, the 2D and 3D static dimensionality types are matched with the ‘correct’ vowel for their shape. That is, round objects are matched with back vowels; spiky objects are matched with front vowels. The 3D GIF, however, is matched with the ‘incorrect’ vowel, serving as the critical trial. This is visualised in Figure 2.

This mismatch tests my primary prediction outlined in section 2. The critical trial tests whether participants map the ‘correct’ vowel quality to a 3D stimulus, even when it is labelled with the ‘incorrect’ vowel quality. This measures whether participants are significantly influenced by dimensionality – labelling the 3D GIF ‘correctly’ regardless of training – or if through learning, they converge toward a different vowel.

Shape	Object	Dimensionality type	Vowel type
Round	Wheel	2D	Back
		3D static	Back
		3D gif	Front
	Glass	2D	Back
		3D static	Back
		3D gif	Front
Succulent	2D	Back	
	3D static	Back	
	3D gif	Front	
Spiky	Knife	2D	Front
		3D static	Front
		3D gif	Back
	Ladder	2D	Front
		3D static	Front
		3D gif	Back
Christmas tree	2D	Front	
	3D static	Front	
	3D gif	Back	

Figure 2: *The initial language in the experiment. The yellow shaded conditions represent critical trials.*

A result supporting my primary prediction would find, for example, the proportion of back vowel productions for a round 3D GIF higher than in any other condition, especially *over* the 3D static image. Since movement (simulated interaction) would be the only difference between 3D static and 3D GIF stimuli, this result would situate this facet of dimensionality – which is most connected to our real-world experiences – as a significant domain influencing cognition.

An especially significant result would find participants converging towards a certain vowel, even if it wasn’t present in the data (e.g., it had disappeared over generations of learning). This would situate the power of the association above the effects of learning.

5 Scope for further work

There is wide scope for studies building on this experiment, particularly those incorporating the cognitive phenomenon of synaesthesia. The literature is rife with discussion on the connection between sound-symbolism and synaesthesia: Bankieris & Simner (2015) note they both have been linked to the left superior parietal cortex; Bankieris & Simner (2015) and Cuskley et al. (2019) suggest that synaesthesia is a latent cognitive function, activated in some but possible in all. Given this neurological linkage, it would be apt to test whether dimensionality would bring to the fore these mechanisms, and if invoking one of sound symbolism and synaesthesia in turn invokes the other. If these phenomena share an apparatus, further study could provide insight into the cognition behind both, and perhaps their interaction with each other.

6 Conclusion

The present proposed experiment fills a gap in the current literature, bringing the bouba/kiki paradigm further into the real world and allowing for a more adequate understanding of the cognitive processes behind sound symbolism. A study such as this may help unravel our cognitive perceptions and conceptualizations of dimensionality, as well as allowing a deeper understanding of how sound-symbolism and dimensionality function – individually, together, and under the influence of iterated learning.

This study is ongoing; future work will focus on data collection and analysis, accompanied by a second write-up detailing results.

7 References

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8 Appendix One: Visual stimuli

<i>Object</i>	<i>2D</i>	<i>3D static</i>	<i>3D GIF</i>
Kitchen knife (classic)			
Ladder (classic)			
Christmas tree (blend)			

Figure A1: Visual stimuli for “spikiness.” Sources cited in references. GIFs I have made myself. Note that GIF format is unsupported by Word; in motion, the GIFs rotate 360° horizontally and vertically.

<i>Object</i>	<i>2D</i>	<i>3D static</i>	<i>3D GIF</i>
Glass (classic)			
Wheel (classic)			
Succulent (blend)			

Figure A2: Visual stimuli for “roundness.” Sources identical to those of Figure A1.

9 Appendix Two: Previous experiment runs

object	label
images/2d_wheel_1.png	sounds/puma.wav
images/3d_wheel.png	sounds/pama.wav
images/wheel.gif	sounds/pima.wav
images/2d_glass_1.png	sounds/buma.wav
images/3d_glass.png	sounds/bama.wav
images/glass.gif	sounds/bima.wav
images/2d_succulent_1.png	sounds/tuma.wav
images/3d_succulent.png	sounds/tama.wav
images/succulent.gif	sounds/tima.wav
images/2d_knife_1.png	sounds/dima.wav
images/3d_knife.png	sounds/dema.wav
images/knife.gif	sounds/duma.wav
images/2d_ladder_1.png	sounds/kima.wav
images/3d_ladder.png	sounds/kema.wav
images/ladder.gif	sounds/kuma.wav
images/2d_christmas_tree_1.png	sounds/gima.wav
images/3d_christmas_tree.png	sounds/gema.wav
images/christmas_tree.gif	sounds/guma.wav

Figure A3: Original input language, generation 0.

participant_id	chain	generation	trial_index	block	time_elapsed	stimulus	sound
ozsite8u7k	1	1	7	observation	25583	images/succulent.gif	sounds/tima.wav
ozsite8u7k	1	1	8	observation	27354	images/2d_christmas_tree_1.png	sounds/gima.wav
ozsite8u7k	1	1	9	observation	28616	images/3d_christmas_tree.png	sounds/gema.wav
ozsite8u7k	1	1	10	observation	29820	images/glass.gif	sounds/bima.wav
ozsite8u7k	1	1	11	observation	30708	images/christmas_tree.gif	sounds/guma.wav
ozsite8u7k	1	1	12	observation	31263	images/3d_knife.png	sounds/dema.wav
ozsite8u7k	1	1	13	observation	32836	images/knife.gif	sounds/duma.wav
ozsite8u7k	1	1	14	observation	33254	images/3d_ladder.png	sounds/kema.wav
ozsite8u7k	1	1	15	observation	33697	images/2d_ladder_1.png	sounds/kima.wav
ozsite8u7k	1	1	16	observation	34147	images/ladder.gif	sounds/kuma.wav
ozsite8u7k	1	1	19	production	45903	images/glass.gif	sounds/ozsite8u7k_0.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	21	production	49403	images/2d_wheel_1.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_1.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	23	production	52892	images/2d_glass_1.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_2.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	25	production	58070	images/knife.gif	sounds/ozsite8u7k_3.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	27	production	63452	images/2d_succulent_1.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_4.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	29	production	67460	images/3d_wheel.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_5.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	31	production	74556	images/succulent.gif	sounds/ozsite8u7k_6.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	33	production	79447	images/3d_knife.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_7.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	35	production	82984	images/christmas_tree.gif	sounds/ozsite8u7k_8.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	37	production	88050	images/3d_glass.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_9.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	39	production	92817	images/ladder.gif	sounds/ozsite8u7k_10.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	41	production	95676	images/2d_knife_1.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_11.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	43	production	100887	images/wheel.gif	sounds/ozsite8u7k_12.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	45	production	104698	images/3d_ladder.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_13.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	47	production	108114	images/3d_christmas_tree.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_14.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	49	production	111521	images/2d_ladder_1.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_15.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	51	production	114235	images/2d_christmas_tree_1.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_16.webm
ozsite8u7k	1	1	53	production	117888	images/3d_succulent.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_17.webm

Figure A4: Generation 1; the first participants' responses.

participant_id	chain	generation	trial_index	block	time_elapsed	stimulus	sound
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	7	observation	106551	images/3d_glass.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_9.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	8	observation	108355	images/2d_succulent_1.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_4.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	9	observation	110140	images/wheel.gif	sounds/ozsite8u7k_12.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	10	observation	111772	images/3d_christmas_tree.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_14.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	11	observation	113370	images/christmas_tree.gif	sounds/ozsite8u7k_8.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	12	observation	114721	images/2d_glass_1.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_2.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	13	observation	116301	images/3d_knife.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_7.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	14	observation	117941	images/ladder.gif	sounds/ozsite8u7k_10.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	15	observation	119660	images/3d_wheel.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_5.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	16	observation	121128	images/2d_knife_1.png	sounds/ozsite8u7k_11.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	19	production	129566	images/knife.gif	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_0.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	21	production	133223	images/3d_glass.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_1.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	23	production	138965	images/3d_wheel.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_2.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	25	production	146078	images/2d_glass_1.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_3.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	27	production	150608	images/2d_succulent_1.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_4.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	29	production	157116	images/3d_ladder.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_5.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	31	production	159992	images/2d_christmas_tree_1.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_6.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	33	production	167022	images/ladder.gif	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_7.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	35	production	169332	images/2d_knife_1.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_8.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	37	production	173699	images/3d_christmas_tree.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_9.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	39	production	178903	images/wheel.gif	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_10.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	41	production	182386	images/christmas_tree.gif	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_11.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	43	production	186524	images/succulent.gif	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_12.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	45	production	189607	images/3d_succulent.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_13.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	47	production	195078	images/glass.gif	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_14.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	49	production	198044	images/2d_wheel_1.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_15.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	51	production	200921	images/2d_ladder_1.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_16.webm
bamm7bvo5j	1	2	53	production	203306	images/3d_knife.png	sounds/bamm7bvo5j_17.webm

Figure A5: *Generation 2; the participant has learned from the previous participant in Generation 1.*

10 Acknowledgements

The present experiment combines aspects of Beckner et al.'s (2017) iterated learning and Loy & Smith's (2020) confederate priming code. I am grateful to them both for the accessibility of their code and encouragement to repurpose and reformulate it.